

1 F162L, 2 L162F, 12 L162V, 1 V162A, 1 V162F, 1 V162I, 16 V162L, 1 V162M



0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 F162L, 2 L162F, 12 L162V, 1 V162A, 1 V162F, 1 V162I, 16 V162L, 1 V162M



- V
- L
- {LV}
- I
- {IV}
- F
- A
- M

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 F162L, 2 L162F, 12 L162V, 1 V162A, 1 V162F, 1 V162I, 16 V162L, 1 V162M



- V
- L
- {LV}
- I
- {IV}
- F
- A
- M

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 F162L, 2 L162F, 12 L162V, 1 V162A, 1 V162F, 1 V162I, 16 V162L, 1 V162M



0 2 4 6 8 10 12